

Social Return on Investment (SROI) for Job Oriented Vocational Trainings: A Study in Selected Development Sector Programmes

¹Dr. Ombir Singh (Head)
Department of Economics, Planning and Development,
Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida, U.P., India

²Mr. Soumen Ghosh (Research Scholar)
School of Management,
Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida, U.P., India

Received: May 11, 2025

Accepted: Jun 9, 2025

Published: Jun 18, 2025

Abstract

Saksham is an initiative, taken by a non-profit organization that aims to empower disadvantaged Indian youth, especially young women, by providing them with vocational skills, facilitating access to decent job opportunities or self-employment to live a life of dignity with economic security, while promoting gender equality & economic security.

To measure the impacts of the program and understand the value that was created, Social Return on Investment (SROI) framework, formalised by Social Value International, was applied. SROI is a measurement valuing both financial and non-financial outcomes of social interventions.

Guided by the eight principles of social value and SROI- i) Involve stakeholders, ii) Understand what changes, iii) Value the things that matter, iv) Only include what is material, v) Do not over claim, vi) Be transparent, vii) Verify the results and viii) Be responsive, the following six stages were followed in calculating the SROI which are i) Establishing scope and identifying stakeholders, ii) Mapping outcomes, iii) Evidencing outcomes and giving them a value, iv) Establishing impact (Deadweight, Attribution, Displacement), v) Calculating the SROI, vi) Reporting, using, and embedding.

The SROI shows that, with an investment of 2.36 Cr. INR, over 76.28 Cr. INR of social value is created, of which 10.36 Cr. INR is directly attributable to Saksham. The SROI ratio is therefore 4.4:1, meaning that for every INR 1 invested, around INR 4.40 of value is created. The analysis suggests that the program contributes towards gender empowerment: more value is created for female students than for male students.

Key Words: Decent work, Economic Security, Vocational Training, Gender Equality, SROI, Development.

Introduction,

India's working-age population (15-59 years) is expected to increase by over 100 million people between 2020-30, which is an advantage as required human resources for various industries are available within the country. Youth comprise a major section of this working-age population. In India Youth is defined as Persons between the age group of 15 and 29 years as per the National Youth Policy 2014. The youth population in India was projected at 371.4 million for the year 2021 and as per the estimates, it will be 345.5 million in 2036. To engage the youth in more meaningful and productive work the government launched the "Skill India Mission" campaign in 2015 with the aim to provide a job-ready workforce to the industry to ramp up productivity and ultimately propel economic growth. The draft National Youth Policy (NYP) 2021 envisages a ten-year vision for youth development that India seeks to achieve by 2030. It is aligned with the SDGs and serves to 'unlock the potential of the youth to advance India'.

Saksham is an initiative, taken by a non-profit organization in 2010 that aims to empower disadvantaged Indian youth, especially young women, by providing them with essential vocational skills that are market-driven, facilitating access to decent job opportunities or self-employment to live a life of dignity with economic security, while promoting gender equality & economic security. The program has been implemented in Delhi, Mumbai, Pune, Bengaluru, and Hyderabad and more than 12,000 young people (60% of females) have graduated from this program and 70% of them have been permanently integrated into wage and self-employment.

The program supports efforts by skilling, reskilling and upskilling target groups on new and green economy livelihoods opportunities to participate in the economy driven by emerging trades and industries. It is also considered to be a central pillar of employability, employment of workers and sustainable enterprise development. By its design and objectives, Saksham program works closely with employers to set training processes so that youth can be provided training as per industry needs, and apart from harmonizing the course delivery to national standards, the program actively endeavours to improve the curriculum as per changing ecosystems, program connects youth with various on-the-job-training and industry visit opportunities as part of apprenticeship. And importantly, program has key result area of providing gainful employment opportunities to youth.

The program is aligned with the National Skilling Agenda as it focuses on the training and employability of youth with an emphasis on girls. The Ministry of Skill Development & Entrepreneurship (MSDE) emphasizes skilling the youth to provide the nation and the world with a large skilled workforce.

Literature Review

The concept was first developed in the 1990s by Jed Emerson and Roberts Enterprise Development Fund (REDF) in the US as a tool to evaluate capital grant requests made by organizations belonging to the REDF's philanthropic portfolio. They incorporated six levels or results of social nature into the calculation of blended value analysis. This index materialized in a ratio that related the costs of the investments with the value of the benefits generated as a modification of the characteristic cost-benefit analysis (CBA). There is a common agreement among SROI academics to track the origins of the methodology back to the year 1997 in the United States of America from (Emerson, Wachowicz, & Chun, 2000) to (Banke-Thomas, Madaj, Charles, & Van Den Broek, 2015).

In 2003, in England, the New Economic Foundation redefined the methodology developed by the REDF by giving greater prominence to stakeholder participation in the development of the whole process of social value assessment. This incorporation of hermeneutic knowledge into the process is how the SROI methodology was born. However, the maturity of the methodology was only reached a few years later when (Nicholls, Lawlor, Neitzert, & Goodspeed, 2009; 2012) established its basic principles and the different phases for its implementation. The application of the SROI analysis looks for two main purposes. First, there is an external purpose that seeks to show the effectiveness of the use of resources to attract funding or to justify the existence of the organization itself (Rauscher, Schober, & Millner, 2012; Rotheroe & Richards, 2007). In addition, there is an internal one that seeks to improve the allocation of resources or to legitimize the performance of the managers themselves (Maier, Schober, Simsa, & Millner, 2015; Ruiz-Lozano, et al., 2020). The ultimate goal of the SROI is to demonstrate, by means of evidence, the sustainability and the social value added by interventions and organizations through the understanding, managing, and communication of their impacts in economic, social, and environmental terms (Maier, Schober, Simsa, & Millner, 2015; Rotheroe & Richards, 2007). To

do so, SROI evaluates the value of the social results created by an intervention or organization by putting them in relation to the costs required to achieve such results. From this point of view, the SROI method is based on a conventional CBA (Walk, Greenspan, Crossley, & Handy, 2015), although it goes a step further by assigning monetary values to other impacts of a social and an environmental nature, both tangible and intangible.

Since its first application, SROI has been gradually modified and integrated with principles and processes usually applied to economic and financial assessments (e.g. return on investment). It aims to assess an intervention under social, economic and environmental points of view, known as the triple bottom line (Norman & MacDonald, 2004), as each investment has to yield social, economic and environmental returns to create blended value (Emerson, 2003). To support practitioners in the implementation of the SROI model, the Social Impact Analysis Association was established in the UK in 2011, and four years later, it merged with the SROI Network in a new organization known as Social Value International (SVI), which represented the governing body of the UK national networks.

SVI developed a principle-based approach comprising seven principles of social value (The SROI Network, 2015): involve stakeholders, understand change, do not overclaim, only include what is material, value what matters, be transparent and verify the result. The implementation of these guiding principles requires the undertaking of six stages: establishing scope and identifying stakeholders, mapping outcomes, evidencing outcomes and then availability, establishing impact, calculating the SROI and reporting and embedding (Nicholls, Lawlor, Neitzert, & Goodspeed, 2012). The function of SROI is to determine and evaluate economic and social value generated by a business, specifically a social venture and also non for profits on a rational and quantifiable grounds (Wilson & Post, 2013).

The SROI is based on a holistic approach to analyze all positive and negative impact (and unintended consequences along the implementation) of the program in three aspects: economic, social and environmental. The method considers also the influence of other external factors or projects. In general, it helps to understand how and why impacts occur (Arvidson, Lyon, McKay, & Moro, 2013; Krlev, Münscher, & Mülberty, 2013). The rationale behind this approach is that

impact has three dimensions, i.e., social, socioeconomic, and economic. The end result of the approach is an equation that depicts the value generated in monetary terms for each unit of money invested in its operations and by its general operations (Di Domenico, Haugh, & Tracey, 2010). SROI is subjective and its success depends on the experience and judgment of experts to identify indicators and financial proxies (Lawlor, Murray, Neitzert, & Sanfilippo, 2008; Arvidson, Lyon, McKay, & Moro, 2013; Jönsson, 2013).

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to assess the social impacts generated by the Saksham program in two locations (Neb Sarai and Prahladpur) in Delhi. The SROI methodology has been applied for the assessment, whose principles and theoretical surroundings have been explained in the section below. The aim of this analysis is to show how the application of the SROI methodology can complement other traditional methods of assessing the impact of Saksham initiatives which focuses on the vocational trainings for the youths to help them getting a job or start an entrepreneurship.

Methodology

For this assessment, the methodology used is the Social Return on Investment (SROI) framework formalized by Social Value International. At its core, SROI is a framework for accounting for value creation, including social, economic, and environmental value considering both financial and non-financial outcomes of social interventions. There are four main elements to how we have measured social value: inputs, outputs, outcomes, and impact (the SROI) as detailed below.

The SROI methodology is based on a series of principles of social value proposed by the SROI network: (a) involve stakeholders, (b) understand what changes, (c) value the things that matter, (d) only include what is material, (e) do not overclaim, (f) be transparent, (g) verify the results, and (h) be responsive. As (Nadotti & Vannoni, 2019) pointed out, the SROI method has the

Value Chain as their theoretical framework, considering an impact as any change on society that derives from outcomes that have been achieved. The above principles are applied in six stages to calculating the SROI that is carried out from the qualitative steps to the quantitative ones, which have been followed in the Saksham SROI evaluation (Nicholls, Lawlor, Neitzert, & Goodspeed, 2012):

1. Establishing scope and identifying stakeholders
2. Mapping outcomes
3. Evidencing outcomes and giving them a value
4. Establishing impact [Deadweight, Attribution, Displacement]
5. Calculating the SROI
6. Reporting, using, and embedding.

SROI is related to both cost-benefit analysis, and sustainability accounting. It emphasizes on social and environmental outcomes, and on primary research with stakeholders, than a traditional cost-benefit approach.

The monetization approach is important to represent all outcomes in the analysis – not just economic outcomes. Monetization of outcomes are done using a monetary value to represent the value of the outcomes to stakeholders. Some outcomes are already expressed in monetary values, for e.g., individual's income. Other outcomes are given a monetary value through the use of a 'financial proxy' – an approximation of the value, which include:

- a. Asking stakeholders directly what they would pay for an outcome – a type of 'stated preference'.
- b. Looking at behaviours of stakeholders – especially how they spend their time and money – a type of revealed preference.

The approach adopted mixed-methods both qualitative and quantitative. It relies on the hermeneutic knowledge of the context and interactions with stakeholders while also offering the economic quantification of the impacts they declare to receive. Based on the theory of change of the program, outcomes were identified through a process of qualitative research with stakeholders. Interviews were conducted with all of the main stakeholder groups: male students, female students, employers, and program implementers.

Quantitative surveys with structured questionnaire was administered with the stakeholders like female and male students and parents of the students. Employers were administered with surveys followed by in-depth interviews. In addition, program implementers were interviewed using IDI guide. The below table depicts the number of stakeholders

Table 1**Stakeholder wise Sample size**

Stakeholders	Numbers	Mode of Data Collection
Female Students	476	Survey
Male Students	594	Survey
Parents	821	Survey
Employer	28	Survey, IDI
Program Implementer	16	IDI

Below are the stakeholders and outcomes that are included in the SROI.

Table 2**Stakeholder wise list of Outcomes**

Stakeholder	Outcome	Number of participants
Female Students	Increased personal income through employment - those who got a job through Saksham	729
	Income given to household - those who got a job through Saksham	729
	Improved personal income through employment - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	201
	Income given to household - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	201
	Improved wellbeing- who reported an improvement in mental health and a reduction in stress / anxiety	1,000
	Improved confidence	1,124
	Improved financial independence	654
	Improved independence / autonomy- students trained by Saksham, who reported that their role / contribution in household decisions has increased	1,574
	Increased wellbeing through improved relationship- students	1,619

	trained by Saksham, who reported that their family members had increased respect for them, and/or their personal decisions, and/or their professional aspirations	
Male students	Increased personal income through employment - those who got a job through Saksham	373
	Income given to household - those who got a job through Saksham	373
	Improved personal income through employment - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	220
	Income given to household - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	220
	Improved wellbeing- who reported an improvement in mental health and a reduction in stress / anxiety	423
	Improved Confidence	696
	Improved Financial independence	453
Households of female students	Increased household income - those who got a job through Saksham	729
	Increased household income - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	201
Households of male students	Increased household income - those who got a job through Saksham	373
	Increased household income - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	220
Employers of students after training program	Reduced training costs - female students who got a job through Saksham	729
	Reduced training costs - male students who got a job through Saksham	373
	Reduced recruitment costs - female students who got a job through Saksham	729
	Reduced recruitment costs - male students who got a job through Saksham	373

Measuring depth of change: Wellbeing Outcomes

The reach calculations show the number of participants benefiting from the outcomes. For the wellbeing outcomes, an estimate needs to be made of the depth of these outcomes. (This is not necessary for the economic outcomes, as the monetary valuation incorporates the depth).

The depth of the outcomes has been estimated by drawing on a study showing the relationship between a person's overall wellbeing, and various other factors (Kulkarni, Kulkarni, Gaiha, & Ima, 2023). Those other factors have a co-efficient that shows the impact of those factors on a person's wellbeing. These factors have been matched to the wellbeing outcomes in the SROI. Factors have been chosen because it was judged that the factor – and its impact on a person's wellbeing – is reasonably similar to the outcome. Inevitably – the link between the factors and the outcomes is stronger in some cases than others.

Table 3
Coefficient

Outcome	Factor	Co-efficient (Depth of change)
Improved wellbeing	Coefficient for: "Conflict in village"	0.01687
Improved confidence	Coefficient for: "Education"	0.0466
Improved financial independence	Coefficient for: "Monthly per capita expenditure"	0.00435
Improved independence / autonomy	Coefficient for: "Newspaper regular women"	0.049
Increased wellbeing through improved relationship	Coefficient for: "Widowed/Divorced"	0.01583

Measuring Impact

i. Deadweight

It is a measure of what would have happened anyway, in the absence of the Saksham program. It is expressed as a percentage of the outcome that would have happened anyway. The calculation uses a question in the surveys for female and male students: *“Imagine what life would have been like if you hadn't undertaken the Saksham program training. Would things have improved, worsened or stayed the same for you?”*

Deadweight is estimated to be 50% for anyone who said “significantly improved”, and 25% for anyone who said “slightly improved”. An average was taken for all female students and all male students. The result was determined as Female students: 0%, Male students: 3.8%

ii. Attribution

It is a measure of how much credit or attribution the Saksham program can take for the outcomes that have been achieved, once deadweight has been considered. The calculation uses a question in the surveys for female and male students: *“To what extent do you think the changes you have described today are due to the Saksham program?”* The initial attribution level is estimated to be 100% for anyone who said “a great deal”, 75% for anyone who said “quite a lot”, 50% for anyone who said “some”, 25% for anyone who said “a little”, and 0% for anyone who said “not at all”. An average was taken for all female students and all male students.

An adjusted attribution level was then calculated. This was because the attribution for outcomes such as gaining employment needs to recognise the contribution of other factors, such as the employer, and former education. A judgement was made that 1/3rd of the overall attribution should go to the employer, 1/3rd to former education and other experiences, and 1/3rd to recent changes for the students (including Saksham). The adjusted attribution level is therefore 1/3rd of the initial attribution level. The result was determined as

Female students: Initial: 81%, Final: 27%

Male students: Initial: 84%, Final: 28%

iii. Displacement

Displacement is a measure of whether any of the value accounted for in the model is not *new* value, but is value that has been moved – or displaced – from someone else or somewhere else. For example, a decrease in crime in one area – due to improved safety features such as street lighting – may lead to an increase in crime in another area as some of the criminal activity.

There is not a consistent displacement rate used in employment SROIs in India. Some have used a 0% displacement rate (Gambhir, Majmudar, Sodhani, & Gupta, 2017). To avoid overclaiming, we have used a figure of 10% for outcomes that arise from gaining employment, drawn from a Department for Work and Pensions (UK) publication (Greenberg, Knight, & Speckess, 2013), that draws on a number of international sources. The report gives displacement estimates for supply-side and demand-side programs. The demand-side example has been used. The paper suggested a range of 0% to 20% - so the mid- point of 10% has been used.

iv. **Discount Rate**

A discount rate of 5% has been used. This means that the value is discounted by 5% for each year in the future that it is accrued. Year 1 value is discounted by 5% once. Year 2 value is discounted by 5% twice, and so on. The 5% figure is regularly used for evaluations in middle-income countries (Haacker, Hallett, & Atun, 2019).

v. **Calculating Monetary Values**

Monetary values for the outcomes were calculated as follows:

Table 4

Monetary value of the Outcomes

Outcome	Approach to monetising the outcome		Result (in INR)
Increased personal income through employment	The difference between annual earnings before Saksham (set as 0 for those who were not employed before Saksham) and current earnings. [Source: Student surveys]	female students getting a job through Saksham;	149,200
		female students getting a job, not through Saksham;	153,726
		male students getting a job through Saksham;	92,086
		male students getting a job, not through Saksham.	77,346
Increased household income (for household); income given to household (for students)	The difference between students' annual contributions to the household income before Saksham, and current contribution. In both instances, this was set as 0 for those who reported that they did not contribute. [Source: Student surveys]	female students getting a job through Saksham;	91,438
		female students getting a job, not through Saksham;	96,316
		male students getting a job through Saksham;	62,009
		male students getting a job, not through Saksham.	70,593
Reduced recruitment costs for employers	The amount that employers report typically spending on recruiting. [Source: Employer survey]		4,594
Reduced training	The difference in training costs for Saksham students, compared to other new employees, as reported by employers.		5,462

costs for employers	[Source: Employer survey]	
Wellbeing outcomes for students	<p>Overall health status (sometimes expressed as a 'Quality Adjusted Life Year' or 'Disability Adjusted Life Year' (QALY or DALY) is valued as 2 x GDP per capita in India.</p> <p>The utility weight for wellbeing is 0.289. This is equivalent to change in mental health from 'severe' to 'slight' in 'Anxiety / depression' domain from the EQ-5D scale. (Source: Euroqol). This means that the share of health status that is equated with wellbeing is 0.289. GDP per capita in India is INR 112,697. (Figure is for 2022. Source: World Bank)</p> <p>The valuation is therefore INR 112,697 x 2 x 0.289, giving a total value of INR 65,139</p>	65,139

vi. **Benefit Period & Drop Off**

The SROI requires a calculation of how long outcomes will last – referred to as the benefit period. In addition, the 'drop off' shows how the value reduces over time. There are two components of drop off considered in this SROI:

- a. **Outcome drop off** – which shows how the amount of outcome reduces over time. For example, some students may gain a job, but then stop working in the future.

1) **Unmarried female students who want to get married**

Two factors affect these students: i) they are likely to get married later, partly due to the intervention of Saksham program, and ii) they are more likely to be able to work once they get married (partner and family are supportive). For this group, the benefit period and drop off are calculated as follows:

- The students are likely to get married three years later than their peers (according to the survey, their preferred marriage age is, on average, three years later than the average marriage age for their peers).
- Most of this group (95%) report in the survey that they would like to continue to work once they are married, and they expect that they will be allowed to continue to work once they are married.
- Therefore, in years 1, 2, and 3, the SROI assumes that all of this group women will continue to work. In years 4 and 5, the SROI assumes that 95% of this group will continue to work

- In total, this group makes up 82% of all female students who got a job.

2) **Unmarried female students who do not want to get married**

- All of the female students who do not want to get married are expected to work for the full five-year benefit period.
- In total, this group makes up 5% of all female students who got a job.

3) **Married female students**

- All of the married female students are expected to be able to work – as they have already gained employment while married and so their partner and family are not a barrier to employment. However, at least some of these students are likely to become mothers relatively soon – and may then exit the labour market – at least temporarily. To account for this, the benefit period has been reduced to 3 years.
- In total, this group makes up 14% of all female students who got a job

4) **Male students**

- All of the male students are expected to work for the full five-year benefit period

- b. **Attribution drop off** – which shows how the amount of attribution that the Saksham can take for the outcome reduces over time.

The SROI model considers attribution drop off – the extent to which the attribution that Saksham can take for the outcomes decreases over time. Once students have gained jobs and entered the workplace, the fact that they are then able to remain in the workplace (in their original job or in a different job) will be increasingly because of the work experience they have gained. Over time, the original training that they received to gain a job will become less important, as their work experience becomes more important. In the model, the training provided by Saksham is considered to be equal to a year's work experience. Therefore:

- In Year 1, Saksham claims 100% of the original attribution level (27% for female students, 28% for male students)
- In Year 2, the attribution is split between the Saksham, and the previous one year's work experience.

Saksham claims 50% of the original attribution level

- In Year 3, the attribution is split between the Saksham, and the previous two years' work experience. Saksham claims 33% of the original attribution level

- In Year 4, the attribution is split between the Saksham, and the previous three years' work experience.

Saksham claims 25% of the original attribution level

- In Year 5, the attribution is split between the Saksham, and the previous four years' work experience. Saksham claims 20% of the original attribution level

Overall, the maximum benefit period considered in this SROI is five years. After five years, the amount of value that is being created, and that Saksham can claim credit for, will be significantly less. In this SROI, benefit period and outcome drop off are considered separately for sub-groups of students – as outlined on the following slide.

Drop Off Summary

Table 5

Drop-off Summary

	Proportion of outcome remaining: Female students	Proportion of outcome remaining: Male students	Proportion of attribution remaining: All students
Year 1	100% (100% of unmarried students who want to get married; 100% of unmarried students who do not want to get married; 100% of married students)	100%	100%
Year 2	100% (100% of unmarried students who want to get married; 100% of unmarried students who do not want to get married; 100% of married students)	100%	50%
Year 3	96% (95% of unmarried students who want to get married; 100% of unmarried students who do not want to get married; 100% of married students)	100%	33%
Year 4	82% (95% of unmarried students who want to get married; 100% of unmarried students who do not want to get married; 0% of married students)	100%	25%
Year 5	82% (95% of unmarried students who want to get married; 100% of unmarried students who do not want to get married; 0% of married students)	100%	20%

Calculations: Impact on Students' Confidence

The example below shows how the first two years' value is calculated for one outcome: improved confidence for female students. Note – some of the figures shown have been rounded. This means that if the calculation is repeated manually, there will be a slight discrepancy in the final figure.

Stakeholder: Female students. **Outcome:** Improved confidence

Year 1

Reach	X Depth	X (1-Dead weight)	X (1-Displacement)	X Attribution	X Financial Proxy	÷ Discount Rate	= Social Value
1,124	X 0.0466	-(1-0)	X (1-0)	X 0.27	INR 65,139	÷ 1.05 ¹	=INR 8,82,710

Year 2

Reach	X Depth	X (1-Dead weight)	X (1-Displacement)	X Attribution	X Financial Proxy	÷ Discount Rate	= Social Value
1,124	X 0.0466	-(1-0)	X (1-0)	X 0.27 X 0.5	INR 65,139	÷ 1.05 ²	= INR 4,20,338

Time Period: This Social Return on Investment (SROI) study investigated the impact of the Saksham program for the period May 2019 to April 2023. The study was conducted in August-October 2023.

Findings & Discussion

The table below shows the value created for each outcome. The table shows both the total value created by the program, and the attributable value created (the value that Saksham can take credit). Results are rounded to the nearest INR 1,00,000.

Value per Outcome

Table: 6

Value per Outcome

Stakeholder	Outcome	Total value created (in INR)	Total attributable value created (in INR)
Female students	Increased personal income through employment - those who got a job through Saksham	39,21,00,000	5,26,00,000
	Income given to household - those who got a job through Saksham	-24,03,00,000	-3,22,00,000
	Improved personal income through employment - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	11,17,00,000	1,50,00,000
	Income given to household - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	-7,00,00,000	-94,00,000
	Improved wellbeing	44,00,000	6,00,000
	Improved confidence	1,37,00,000	18,00,000
	Improved financial independence	7,00,000	1,00,000
	Improved independence / autonomy	2,01,00,000	27,00,000
	Increased wellbeing through improved relationship	67,00,000	9,00,000
Male students	Increased personal income through employment - those who got a job through Saksham	12,86,00,000	1,71,00,000
	Income given to household - those who got a job through Saksham	-8,66,00,000	-1,15,00,000
	Improved personal income through employment - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	6,39,00,000	85,00,000

	Income given to household - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	-5,83,00,000	-78,00,000
	Improved wellbeing	18,00,000	2,00,000
	Confidence	81,00,000	11,00,000
	Financial independence	5,00,000	1,00,000
Households of female students	Increased household income - those who got a job through Saksham	24,03,00,000	3,22,00,000
	Increased household income - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	7,00,00,000	94,00,000
Households of male students	Increased household income - those who got a job through Saksham	8,66,00,000	1,15,00,000
	Increased household income - those who got a job NOT through Saksham	5,83,00,000	78,00,000
Employers of students after training program	Reduced training costs - female students who got a job through Saksham	10,36,00,000	10,00,000
	Reduced training costs - male students who got a job through Saksham	5,09,00,000	5,00,000
	Reduced recruitment costs - female students who got a job through Saksham	6,40,00,000	9,00,000
	Reduced recruitment costs - male students who got a job through Saksham	3,14,00,000	4,00,000

The largest beneficiaries of the program are the households of the students – as both male and female students contribute a large share of their income to their households. More value is created for female students overall than for male students. There are two reasons: i) More female students participate in the program, ii) Some of the male students were already in employment, but the increase in their salary when they get a new job is lower.

Value per Stakeholder

Table 7
Value per Stakeholder

Outcome	Total value created	Total attributable value created
Female students	23,92,00,000	3,21,00,000
Male students	5,80,00,000	78,00,000
Households of female students	31,03,00,000	4,16,00,000
Households of male students	14,49,00,000	193,00,000
Employers	1,04,00,000	29,00,000
Total	76,28,00,000	10,36,00,000

SROI Ratio

- In total, over INR 76.28 Cr. INR of social value was created by the program, of which INR 10,00,00,000 was directly attributable to Saksham.
- The investment in Saksham was INR 2,36,53,300.

The SROI ratio is therefore 4.4:1, meaning that for every INR 1 invested in Saksham, around INR 4.40 of value is created.

Conclusion

- The SROI shows that Saksham creates social value for various stakeholder groups. In particular, the analysis suggests that Saksham contributes towards gender empowerment: more value is created for female students than for male students.
- Comparing SROI ratios is challenging, as different SROI analyses include and exclude different outcomes, and will have different assumptions. Saksham's SROI ratio of 4.4:1 is considered to be very strong. The ratio is significantly above 1:1, suggesting that Saksham represents good value for money.

Limitations of the Study

1. There are some areas that are beyond the scope of the SROI that might create further value – especially any impact on attitudes towards women in the workplace and women's empowerment more broadly. Understanding this is beyond the scope of an SROI study such as this one.

2. There are ways that the SROI approach could be strengthened in the future. For example:
 - a. The measurement of wellbeing outcomes might be improved. In particular, if a baseline measure of wellbeing could be taken, then this would allow for a more accurate measurement and valuation of wellbeing outcomes. This might include the use of standardised tools (such as the WHO-5 wellbeing measure, or the Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale), and/or bespoke measures to capture outcomes that are specific to the Saksham program.
 - b. Longer-term follow-up with students would allow a more accurate assessment of the benefit period and drop off.
3. SROI analyses inevitably involve some assumptions. For example, in the Saksham SROI, it is assumed that female students reporting on when they wish to get married, and whether they will be able to work once they are married, reflect the reality of their situation. These assumptions might be improved with further long-term data collection.

References

- Arvidson, M., Lyon, F., McKay, S., & Moro, D. (2013). Valuing the social? The nature and controversies of measuring Social Return on Investment (SROI). *Voluntary Sector Review*, 4(1): 3-18.
- Banke-Thomas, A., Madaj, B., Charles, A., & Van Den Broek, N. (2015). Social return on investment (SROI) methodology to account for value for money of public health interventions: A systematic review. *BMC Public Health*, 15(1), Article 582.
- Di Domenico, M., Haugh, H., & Tracey, P. (2010). Social bricolage: Theorizing social value creation in social enterprises. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 34(4), 681703. doi:10.1111/j.1540-6520.2010.00370.x.
- Emerson, J. (2003). The blended value proposition: integrating social and financial returns. *California Management Review*, Vol. 45 No. 4, pp. 35-51.
- Emerson, J., Wachowicz, J., & Chun, S. (2000). Social return on investment: Exploring aspects of value creation in the nonprofit sector. *Roberts Foundation*.
- Gambhir, V., Majmudar, N., Sodhani, S., & Gupta, N. (2017). Social Return on Investment (SROI) for Hindustan Unilever's (HUL) CSR initiative on livelihoods (Prabhat). *Procedia Computer Science*, 122, pp. 556–563. doi:10.1016/j.procs.2017.11.406.
- Greenberg, D., Knight, G., & Speckess, S. (2013). *Improving DWP assessment of the relative costs and benefits of employment programmes (WP100)*. Retrieved from GOV.UK.: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/improving-dwp-assessment-of-the-relative-costs-and-benefits-of-employment-programmes-wp100> (accessed on 25 August 2023)

- Haacker, M., Hallett, T., & Atun, R. (2019). *On discount rates for economic evaluations in Global Health*. Retrieved from OUP Academic: <https://academic.oup.com/heapol/article/35/1/107/5591528> (Accessed on 25 November 2023)
- Jardine, C., & Whyte, B. (2013). Valuing desistence? A social return on investment case study of a through care project for short-term prisoners. *Social and Environmental Accountability Journal*, 33(1), 20– 32.
- Jönsson, J. (2013). Social Return on Investment: rooms for improvement & research – A background study on SROI to identify research gaps. *Forum for social innovation Sweden*, Retrieved from http://socialinnovation.se/wpcontent/uploads/2013/10/Rooms-for-improvement-andresearch_A4_lowres_131024.pdf.
- Krlev, G., Münscher, R., & Mülbert, K. (2013). Social Return on Investment (SROI): State-of-the-Art and Perspectives. *CSI Report*, Retrieved from http://archiv.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/volltextserver/18758/1/CSI_SROI_Meta_Analysis_2013.pdf.
- Kulkarni, V., Kulkarni, V., Gaiha, R., & Ima, K. (2023, August 25). *Changes in subjective well-being in India-Social Indicators Research*. Retrieved from Springer: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11205-023-03115-8>
- Lawlor, E., Murray, R., Neitzert, E., & Sanfilippo. (2008). Investing for Social Value: Measuring social return on investment for the Adventure Capital Fund. *New Economics Foundation*, Retrieved from http://socialvalueuk.org/publications/publications/cat_view/25-other-publications?start=5.
- Maier, F., Schober, C., Simsa, R., & Millner, R. (2015). SROI as a method for evaluation research: Understanding merits and limitations. *VOLUNTAS: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations*, 26(5), 1805–1830.
- Nadotti, L., & Vannoni, V. (2019). Cultural and event tourism: An interpretative key for impact assessment. *Eastern Journal of European Studies*, 10(1), 115–131.
- Nicholls, J., Lawlor, E., Neitzert, E., & Goodspeed, T. (2009). *A guide to social return on investment*. Office of the Third Sector, Cabinet Office.
- Nicholls, J., Lawlor, E., Neitzert, E., & Goodspeed, T. (2012). Guide to Social Return on Investment. *The SROI Network*, Office of the Third Sector, UK, ISBN: 978-0-9562274-0-9.
- Norman, W., & MacDonald, C. (2004). Getting to the bottom of 'triple bottom line'. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 243-262, doi: 10.5840/beq200414211.
- Rauscher, O., Schober, C., & Millner, R. (2012). Social Impact Measurement and Social Return on Investment (SROI)-analysis: New methods of economic evaluation. https://www.socialvalueuk.org/app/uploads/2016/03/Social-Impact-Measurement-and-SROI_English_Version_final_2.pdf.
- Rotheroe, N., & Richards, A. (2007). Social return on investment and social enterprise: Transparent accountability for sustainable development. *Social Enterprise Journal*, 3(1), 31–48.
- Ruiz-Lozano, M., Tirado-Valencia, P., Sianes, A., Ariza-Montes, A., Fernández-Rodríguez, V., & López-Martín, M. (2020). SROI methodology for public administration decisions about financing with social criteria. A case study. *Sustainability*, 12(3), 1070.

Walk, M., Greenspan, I., Crossley, H., & Handy, F. (2015). Social return on investment analysis. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 26(2), 129–144.

Wilson, F., & Post, J. (2013). Business models for people, planet (& profits): Exploring the phenomena of social business, a market-based approach to social value creation. *Small Business Economics*, 40(3), 715737. doi:10.1007/s11187-011-9401-0.